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INNOVATION FOR TOMORROW: PROGRESS IN SAFE AND SUSTAINABLE CONCEPTS

ABSTRACT BOOK

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1.01.T-05 Beyond Exposure: Investigating the Transgenerational Effects of Bisphenol S in Zebrafish

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Bisphenol S (BPS), a commonly used substitute for Bisphenol A (BPA), has been detected in surface waters at increasing concentrations (from ng/L to low µg/L), primarily due to its widespread industrial applications, especially in the production of polycarbonate plastics and epoxy resins. As current knowledge regarding the toxicity of BPS in non-target organisms is limited, therefore, this study aims to evaluate the ecological risks of BPS in aquatic ecosystems through a transgenerational bioassay with *Danio rerio* (zebrafish) as a model organism. The first generation (F0) was exposed to environmentally relevant concentrations of BPS (0.4, 2, and 10 µg/L direct exposure) and subsequent generations, F1 and F2, were grown in clean water (intergenerational and transgenerational, respectively). We characterized physiological, biochemical and molecular responses to disclose cause-effects relationships and contribute to the understanding of the underlying mechanisms behind the adverse physiological responses. In F0, a significant decrease in the fertilization rate was observed and several biochemical biomarkers (i.e. catalase, glutathione S-transferase and acetylcholinesterase) were altered by the lowest and highest concentrations, in both males and females brains. Parental BPS exposure altered several endpoints in non-directly exposed zebrafish (F1 and F2), by affecting their growth, heart rate, behaviour and other physiological parameters such as Fulton's condition factor, gonadosomatic and hepatosomatic indexes. To better understand the observed effects described so far, we began by performing a transcriptomic analysis (RNA-seq) on F1 embryos at 24 hpf. F1 embryos descendant from parental exposure to 0.4 µg/L of BPS, were the ones that revealed the largest number of altered genes compared to the control group. The majority of those were downregulated and 8 KEGG pathways were affected, such as oxidative phosphorylation, RNA degradation, ribosome, cardiac muscle contraction and PPAR signalling pathway. Results so far suggest that BPS, at environmentally relevant concentrations, was capable of inducing several direct, inter and transgenerational effects in different biological processes in zebrafish. Therefore, with this conceptual approach, we also hope to promote the assessment of the environmental hazards and risks of this compound. This study is supported by the project TRANSEPIC (2022.02922.PTDC, doi: 10.54499/2022.02925.CEECIND/CP1728/CT0004) and the author Marta Ribeiro acknowledges the Portuguese Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia for her PhD grant (2022.12763.BD)

1.01.P Unveiling Long-Term Ecological Impacts: From Epigenetic Biomarkers to Multigenerational and Chronic Effects of Environmental Contaminants Including Their Mixtures

1.01.P-Tu001 Sub-lethal Effects of Cadmium and Ciprofloxacin in Freshwater Green Microalgae: Epigenetic and Phenotypic Responses

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Anthropogenic activities often lead to contamination of waters with harmful substances such as metals, pharmaceuticals and other exogenous chemicals. As epigenetic mechanisms shape gene-environment interactions, the study of the epigenetic alterations in these organisms can provide clues to better understand how they face environmental challenges and how to protect them. Assuming the importance of microalgae as producers in freshwater food chains, we assessed the effects in *Parachlorella* sp. of exposure (10 days) to sublethal levels of cadmium, a legacy environmental contaminant, and ciprofloxacin, an antibiotic that has been recognised as an emerging contaminant in freshwater (yield EC20 after testing according to the OECD guideline no. 201; 90.3 µg Cd/L and 7.68 mg ciprofloxacin/L). We comparatively followed total DNA methylation and several phenotypic endpoints, namely DNA damage (comet assay), physiological (growth, efficiency of photosystem II and oxygen production were assessed) and biochemical biomarkers (oxidative stress and damage). Cadmium tended to induce hypomethylation and ciprofloxacin hypermethylation of the microalgae genome. Both chemicals induced a slight decrease in biomass yield but there were no effects or slight stimulation in photosystem II efficiency and oxygen

production. Both chemicals caused mild oxidative stress and genotoxicity. Whole transcriptome analysis (RNAseq) and assessment of DNA methylation at the cytosine level (EM-seq) are ongoing, which should provide evidence on the mechanistic behind the phenotypic effects noticed and changes promoted by cadmium and ciprofloxacin in DNA methylation patterns. The molecular basis for adverse outcome pathways of toxicity caused by stressors such cadmium and ciprofloxacin in microalgae will certainly be better characterized, allowing a feasible selection of appropriate biomarkers for improved ecological risk assessment and the consequent protection of microalgae. This work was developed under the scope of project EPIBOOST, funded by the EU - Grant 101078991. AP is funded by FCT - 2022.10817.BD. JL was funded by national funds (OE), through FCT - framework contract foreseen in Decree- Law 57/2016, changed by Law 57/2017. SF was supported by FCT Individual Call to Scientific Employment Stimulus (DOI: 10.54499/2021.02653.CEECIND/CP1659/CT0012).

1.01.P-Tu002 Impact of Endocrine Disrupting Chemicals on Reproduction and Intergenerational Inheritance of Epigenetic Traces in the Freshwater Snail *Biomphalaria glabrata*

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Endocrine disrupting chemicals (EDCs) are found ubiquitously in the environment, as anthropogenic deposition has increased immensely in recent decades. They mimic or inhibit endogenous hormones and negatively impact the health of an organism through various modes of action. For example, EDCs have been shown to affect epigenetic mechanisms, which cause phenotype changes and inheritance of traits not associated with DNA sequence alteration. In this study, we investigated the effects of acute and chronic as well as direct and indirect endocrine disruption on the reproduction of the pulmonate freshwater snail *Biomphalaria glabrata* in two consecutive generations. A putative impact of estrogenic disruption in molluscs is of particular interest as this phylum has developed a distinct sexual hormone system. Nevertheless, it belongs to one of the largest classes within the animal kingdom being exposed to estrogenic substances. *Biomphalaria glabrata* individuals of the F0 generation were exposed to different concentrations of the endocrine active substance 17 β -estradiol and changes on reproduction were determined. Transcriptome analysis revealed distinct sets of differentially expressed genes in ovotestes (gonads) after a short (24 hours) and a long (28 days) exposure, while global DNA methylation was not significantly changed in this tissue. Next, long-term effects of endocrine disruption and putative intergenerational inheritance of epigenetic changes were determined. The offspring (F1) of the exposed F0 individuals were either raised without or with continuous exposure to 17 β -estradiol. Development and reproductive fitness as well as global DNA methylation of both cohorts were determined and revealed a significant negative effect of both, a direct and indirect 17 β -estradiol exposure, on the F1 generation. In summary, our data suggest that the freshwater snail *Biomphalaria glabrata* is sensitive to estrogenic disrupting chemicals and that intergenerational adverse effects could be explained by a changed DNA methylome.

1.01.P-Tu003 Multigeneration Responses of *Folsomia candida* to Short Chain Per- and Polyfluorinated Substances (PFAS)

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Due to the high persistence of per- and polyfluorinated substances (PFAS), organisms living in contaminated environments are chronically exposed to these chemicals over multiple generations. Yet, such chronic effects have barely been addressed in ecotoxicity experiments. Moreover, existing data on PFAS ecotoxicity is strongly biased towards the aquatic environment and to long-chain compounds, although short-chain PFAS have been widely used as substitutes for long-chain PFAS, resulting in high emissions into the environment. Therefore, this study aimed to assess the ecotoxicity of the short-chain PFAS perfluorobutane sulfonic acid (PFBS) and its precursor perfluorobutane sulfonamide (FBSA) to the soil invertebrate *Folsomia candida* (Collembola) over five consecutive generations, with adult survival, reproduction and population growth rate as endpoints. The tests followed OECD guideline 232, with slight modifications. In the multigeneration tests, PFBS did not significantly affect adult survival and population growth rate at the highest test concentration (1160 mg kg⁻¹ dry soil), but had a mild effect on reproduction, with EC50 values for reproduction of 700, 866 and 710 mg kg⁻¹ dry soil for the F0, F2, and F4 generation, respectively. FBSA was substantially more toxic than PFBS. Full concentration-effect relationships were obtained for all test endpoints for the F0 generations exposed to FBSA, with an LC50 of 10.3 mg kg⁻¹ dry soil, an EC50 of 1.43 mg kg⁻¹ dry soil for reproduction and an EC50 of 1.89 mg kg⁻¹ dry soil for population growth rate. Since *F. candida* exposed to 9.64 and 92.7 mg kg⁻¹ dry soil FBSA

Background

Anthropogenic activities often lead to contamination of waters. Assuming the importance of microalgae as primary producers in freshwater food chains, we assessed the effects in *Parachlorella* sp. of exposure to sublethal levels of cadmium, a legacy environmental contaminant, and ciprofloxacin, an antibiotic that has been recognised as an emerging contaminant in freshwater. As epigenetic mechanisms shape gene-environment interactions, the study of the epigenetic alterations in these organisms can provide clues to better understand how they face environmental challenges and how to protect them.

Aim

To perform a comparative study between epigenetic biomarkers (total DNA methylation) and several phenotypic endpoints, namely DNA damage (comet assay), physiological (growth, efficiency of photosystem II and oxygen production) and biochemical biomarkers (oxidative stress and damage).

Methods

1 Exposure

OECD guideline no. 201^[1]

	EC ₂₀
Cadmium	90.3 µg L ⁻¹
Ciprofloxacin	7.68 mg L ⁻¹

10-day exposure

2 Biomarkers

Epigenetic

- CH₃ DNA Methylation
- EpigenTek™ MethylFlash Global DNA Methylation ELISA kit
- Whole transcriptome analysis RNA-seq (ongoing)
- Assessment of DNA methylation at the cytosine level EM-seq (ongoing)

Biochemical

- Antioxidant enzymes activity Colorimetric assay
- Lipid peroxidation (TBARS) Colorimetric assay

Genotoxicity

- DNA damage levels Alkaline comet assay

Physiological

- Growth Biomass growth - yield
- Efficiency of photosynthetic activity Measurement of maximum quantum yield of PSII
- Oxygen production Measurement of oxygen concentration

Results

Epigenetic

Cadmium

Ciprofloxacin

Physiological

Genotoxicity

Biochemical

Figure 1. Biomarkers measured in *Parachlorella* sp. exposed to 90.3 µg L⁻¹ of cadmium (yellow, left) and 7.68 mg L⁻¹ of ciprofloxacin (green, right) for 10 days. Epigenetic biomarkers: total 5-mC levels (A1, A2); Physiological biomarkers: biomass yield (B1, B4), maximum quantum efficiency of Photosystem II (B2, B5) and oxygen concentration (B3, B6); Genotoxicity assay: DNA damage levels (C1, C2); Biochemical biomarkers: antioxidant enzymes activity (D1-D4, D6, D7) and TBARS levels (D5, D8). CTL – control group, non-exposed organisms; EC₂₀ – exposed organisms. Error bars correspond to standard error of the mean values; * represents statistical differences (Independent samples T-test or Mann-Whitney U test, p < 0.05).

- Cadmium exposure led to non-significant global genome hypomethylation and ciprofloxacin led to hypermethylation.
- Cadmium induced a slight decrease in biomass yield, while ciprofloxacin stimulated the biomass yield, and both chemicals caused a slight stimulation in PS II efficiency.
- Both chemicals showed no significant impact in respiration and oxygen concentration in the medium.
- Both chemicals caused mild genotoxicity.
- Cadmium caused mild oxidative stress; ciprofloxacin did not show an obvious trend regarding oxidative stress.
- Whole transcriptome analysis (RNAseq) and assessment of DNA methylation at the cytosine level (EM-seq) are ongoing, which should provide evidence on the mechanistic behind the phenotypic effects noticed and changes promoted by cadmium and ciprofloxacin in DNA methylation patterns.

References

[1] OECD (2011) Test No. 201: Freshwater Alga and Cyanobacteria, Growth Inhibition Test. OECD Guidelines for the Testing of Chemicals, Section 2, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264069923-en>.

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Takeaway message

These results, combined with ongoing work on the molecular basis, contribute to the understanding of adverse outcome pathways of toxicity caused by stressors such as cadmium and ciprofloxacin in green microalgae, allowing a feasible selection of appropriate biomarkers for improved ecological risk assessment.